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CONTINUOUS REFLECTION USING AN E-PORTFOLIO IMPROVES STUDENTS' LEADERSHIP BEHAVIOUR

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ABSTRACT

Knowledge, skills, and abilities in communication and project management and the application of these basics to facilitate teamwork and leadership are necessary for both professionals and students of higher education in all science and engineering fields.

Leadership education has usually been limited to simple acquisition of knowledge in a classroom-setting, and a major issue has emerged concerning transfer of classroom-acquired knowledge into real-life practice. Leadership education has been conducted for ten years for first-year Master's students at the Graduate School of Engineering and Science at the Shibaura Institute of Technology. The program has five modules: knowledge, training by simulation, real action, reflection, and assessment. Because students have limited opportunities to learn from real leaders and demonstrate leadership behaviours, we utilised a simulator to enhance students' experiences in a safe environment by having them review their own behaviour with an e-portfolio. Students are likely to be less hesitant to take leadership initiatives after repeated simulations. The purpose of this study was to positively change leadership behaviour of students by allowing them to practise reflection with the e-portfolio. The students followed prompts concerning reflection on their behaviour in the e-portfolio, during a seven-week period. To verify the educational outcomes of learning, questionnaire surveys were conducted on 'changes in interpretation of leadership concepts,' 'changes in leadership behaviour through continuous recording in the e-portfolio,' and 'leadership self-efficacy.' Results highlighted the potential of continuous reflection using the e-portfolio for positive changes in learners' leadership behaviour.

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1 INTRODUCTION

All engineering students need to develop their important skills of leadership in project management. Leadership education has been conducted for first-year students of the Master's program at the Shibaura Institute of Technology's Graduate School of Engineering and Science for over ten years. Because students have limited opportunities to learn from hands-on leadership experience, we utilise a simulator to increase students' experience in a safe environment. A student is less hesitant to take leadership actions following repeated practice in simulations. The program has five modules: knowledge, training by simulation, real action, reflection, and assessment. The e-portfolio was introduced to invite students to review their behaviour. Leadership, which is the core of this research, is a highly interdisciplinary theme that has been studied in multiple fields such as psychology, business administration, and educational technology. At present, leadership research is being transformed from exploring what leadership is to the development of leadership. Learning from experience is gaining attention as an excellent way for leaders to grow, and empirical research on leadership development through experience learning is progressing. These studies have shown the importance of reflection on experience [1]. The process of reflection is important to promote effective reflection from experience. For the learning through experience process, Kolb constructed a four-stage learning cycle: 'concrete experience', 'reflective observation', 'abstract conceptualisation', and 'active experimentation'. This model has recently been widely used in teacher education and nursing [2]. Many universities in the United States, which is known for good leadership education, use the Social Change Model of Leadership Development as a basis for building programs. One of the seven components of the model, the consciousness of self, is positioned as the basis for realising all other components. Effective reflection methods for raising self-awareness include conscious observation of current self-thinking, feelings and behaviour, receiving feedback from others, and keeping a diary [3]. As described above, it is clear that reflection is important in the process of turning experience into learning in leadership training. However, the methods and processes of reflection to enhance positive leadership behaviour have not been clarified. This research focuses not only on shallow reflections of only the facts experienced, but also on deep reflections that change student behaviour. The central question in this study is 'What kind of process reflection is effective in bringing positive change to student leadership behaviour?'

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Definition of leadership

In this education, leadership is defined as a relational process of people attempting to accomplish change or make a difference to benefit the common good together [4]. In addition, leadership is not an ability bestowed upon a special person, but rather for everyone to exhibit and develop.

2.2 Leadership educational objective and the level of study

Educational objective

The educational objectives are shown below:

- To understand the systematic knowledge needed when implementing project activities.
- To practise skills and leadership within the technical areas of science and engineering.
- To understand one's own skills and to set up a behavioural objective.

Style of teaching and learning

Education and learning styles are shown in Table 1.

The outcome of learning is gradually established in the following order: 1. Knowledge → 2. Consciousness → 3. Action → 4. Mastery.

Table 1. Learning styles combined for leadership education.

		Lecture	Simulator	Practice
Merits		Deep knowledge	Many simulated experiences	Real experience
Demerits		Passive learning	Virtual	No second chance
Outcome of learning	1. Knowledge acquisition	xxx	x	
	2. conceiving leadership	xx	xxx	xx
	3. Acting		xx	xx
	4. Mastery		xx	xxx

** The number of x represents the extent of suitability of each teaching methodology for a desired outcome. The higher the x score, the more suitable the teaching methodology is for a desired outcome. The most suitable methodology for varying types of outcome is as follows: a lecture, for acquisition of the knowledge; a simulator, for conceiving leadership; and practice, for achieving mastery of skills and techniques.*

Although a lecture is suitable for giving systematic knowledge, it is difficult to include activities in which students can practise action. A simulation exercise has the effect of raising awareness of daily improvement and the necessity for new action as a result of self-reflection. Although practice aims at the mastery of the skill, a long period of time is required to achieve a learning outcome. Each educational style has a mutually complementary relationship, and they can achieve results by working together. Based on this plan, the leadership educational model in Figure 1 was designed.

2.3 Leadership education model

The leadership education model (Fig. 1) has five modules: knowledge, training by simulation, real action, reflection, and assessment [5]. At the start of a program, diagnostic evaluation is conducted. Next, a student enters a cycle of skill acquisition.

The first step is for students to gain knowledge in the leadership arena through lectures. Then, they utilise simulation to experience leadership actions many times. Simulation provides a safe environment in which they can try many different approaches in taking leadership in various situations. A simulation exercise has the effect of raising awareness of daily improvement and the necessity for new action as a result of self-reflection, all of which stem from the various virtual experiences.

Fig. 1. Leadership education model

Table 2. Leadership behaviours targeted in PBL activities

#	Four components	Specific leadership behaviours
1	Goal setting and achievement	I can devise my work to contribute to an activity in a project
2		I can understand specific situational requirements and encourage project members to achieve their goals
3		I can contribute to a project and achieve results through work
4	Communication and problem solving	I can share knowledge and technology with a project member positively, and can strengthen a mutual relationship
5		I can discern the cause of a problem, acquire pertinent information, and determine a solution
6		I can carry out activities for the smooth progress of a project
7	Proposal of ideas and ability for planning	I can coordinate socially relevant research tasks and plant the seeds of scientific innovation
8		I can propose an idea with confidence in a timely manner

9		I can create a plan foreseeing short- and long-term research results
10	Understanding the situation/building relationships	I can manage my and others' ability to cope with high pressure situations or rapidly changing environmental conditions
11		I can engage a project member in conversation, listen attentively and positively, and show sympathy
12		I can raise motivation by managing a project member's level of stress

In the next step, students as a team utilise PBL (Project Based Learning) so that the above simulated experiences can help them show leadership. Students can apply their leadership training in actual projects, and this increases their leadership skills. It is highly effective to apply conscious leadership to a project aimed at a specific goal in limited circumstances. Table 2 shows the specific leadership behaviours that students aim to practice in PBL activities. This education repeats both of the steps above, thus raising leadership abilities in an upward spiral. Furthermore, the learner reflects on the simulated experience and the action in practice, and identifies the skill correction component and the skill that needs training. In the end, students complete a comprehensive evaluation. This paper focuses on the reflection component. In particular, this study focuses on individual reflection. The e-portfolio was used as a tool to promote reflection. Over a period of seven weeks, on a weekly basis, students recorded and reflected on their leadership experiences in the e-portfolio.

2.4 Education using simulation

Students who lack experience have huge gaps between knowledge and action and this makes it impossible for them to immediately turn knowledge into action. Therefore, we utilise simulation as a means to bridge these gaps [6]. This simulator was developed with the aim of strengthening interpersonal skills and acquiring leadership skills to involve the members around them in achieving goals. The training of the simulator aims to ensure that repeated thoughts and actions are ingrained in the body and eventually they come out naturally without being conscious of them as actual actions. The simulated experiences that students acquire through repetitive practice can provide a smooth bridge to reality.

2.5 Setting reflection prompts

Students recorded and reviewed their leadership experience in the e-portfolio once a week for seven weeks. The portfolio has the following prompts to encourage reflection:

- 1) What happened? (What needs improvement?)
- 2) What were your feelings and thoughts at that time?
- 3) Where do you think the cause of the failure was?
- 4) What are the lessons learnt from the experience?
- 5) What action do you want to try next time for better results?

3 OUTLINE OF SURVEY

3.1 Survey target

The purpose of this study is to clarify changes in students' interpretations of leadership over the course of seven weeks of leadership practice and the effects of continuous recording in e-portfolios.

The subjects of the survey were 89 first-year Master's students in the Graduate School of Engineering and Science, who were trainees in the required subject 'Advanced Systems Engineering'.

3.2 Survey timing and method

A questionnaire survey was conducted at the midpoint of seven weeks of leadership practice (four weeks after the start). The questionnaire was distributed on the Learning Management System (LMS) and the students answered on the LMS. Answering was optional and, as a result, responses were obtained from 22 people (response rate 25%).

3.3 Survey contents

The following four questions were asked in the questionnaire survey.

Question 1: How do you interpret leadership? Has it changed from your previous interpretation?

Question 2: You have recorded your leadership experience and results of your reflections in your portfolio. Please describe how your feelings, thoughts, or actions have changed as a result of this continuous recording.

Question 3: In your leadership practice, how strongly do you feel that you are actually able to implement what you have just learned in your leadership practice? Please choose one from the following: Very strong; Strong; Moderate; Not much; Not at all.

Question 4: How much do you want to improve your leadership? Please choose one from the following: Very strong; Strong; Moderate; Not much; Not at all.

4 RESULTS

The results for Question 1 are shown in Table 3. Regarding the interpretation of leadership, comparison was made between before and during the course (4 weeks after the start). Twenty out of 22 (91%) responded that there was a change, and two with no change.

Thirteen out of the 20 people who changed had perceived leadership as a skill that one person in the team possesses before attending the course. Specifically, there were descriptions such as 'I thought that leadership belongs only to the leader', 'I thought that leadership was an innate ability', and 'One person who puts together a team'. Four weeks later, these interpretations changed to recognition that leadership was a quality for all members of the group, and that skills could be acquired through training. Specific descriptions included 'the abilities required of all members, not just leaders,' 'skills that each member should understand and demonstrate,' and 'anyone can acquire that ability through practice.'

Next, an excerpt of the results for Question 2 is shown in Table 4. This is a description of changes in students' feelings, ideas, and behaviours due to the continuous reflection on leadership experience in PBL activities recorded once a week. Out of 22, 21 (95%) showed specific changes, and one answered no change.

Finally, Table 5 shows the results of Questions 3 and 4. The following two items were cross tabulated: the degree of feeling that following the leadership practice that they were likely to do well; and their willingness to increase their leadership skills. Fifteen out of 22 (68%) were willing to increase leadership. However, in the leadership practice, eight people (36%) answered that they seemed to do well. In addition, all four students who answered that their motivation for improvement was 'very strong' answered that they were 'strong' about the feeling that they seemed able to do well. In contrast, 11 students who answered that they had a 'strong' desire to improve had different results about their confidence that they could do well, specific details were as follows: two people for 'strong', six for 'moderate', and three for 'not so much'.

Table 3. *The transformation of leadership concepts through leadership education (excerpt)*

#	Before class starts	Four weeks after
1	Charismatic skills that only certain people have	Skills that can be acquired through training
2	What a single leader exercises	Exercise by all members participating in the project
3	How leaders can organise members	Anyone can improve by practising repeatedly over and over instead of innate ability
4	What the best people in the team demonstrate	It can be demonstrated to anyone depending on the training and effort of the person
5	A team needs a single leader	Everyone in the group demonstrates leadership

Table 4. *Changes in feelings, thoughts, and behaviours caused by continuing to record in the portfolio (excerpt)*

1	In every PBL class, I became aware of leadership. I feel more responsible that I have to be more active in the project than before. I had the habit of thinking about the project outside of class
2	I thought it was important to always look back on my behaviour using the portfolio, reflect on and improve, and gain leadership. At the same time, I feel it is difficult to acquire leadership
3	I have a clear understanding of my shortcomings and what I need to improve next time. It has become clear what action to take during group discussions in the exercises

4	We now take time to look back after the exercise discussions to record in the portfolio. As a result, I feel that the content of the discussion has become more organised and that I have been able to produce various ideas. As I reflected not only on the content of the discussion but also on my actions, remarks, and behaviours, I began to improve areas that I felt needed improvement
5	I have accumulated what I need to gain leadership. In particular, I feel that the depth of discussion, the morale of members, and the speed of work change depended on the presence or absence of leadership. Recently, I have begun to be conscious of paying attention to the other person's feelings during discussions

Table 5. Numbers of responses cross tabulated for Questions 3 and 4.

Question 4: How much do you want to improve your leadership?	Question 3: How strongly do you feel that you are actually able to implement what you have just learned in your leadership practice?					
	1 Very strongly	2 Strongly	3 Moderate	4 Not much	5 Not at all	Total
1 Very strongly	0	0	0	1	0	1
2 Strongly	4	2	1	0	0	7
3 Moderate	0	6	2	0	0	8
4 Not much	0	3	2	1	0	6
5 Not at all	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	4	11	5	2	0	22

5 DISCUSSION

The purpose of this study was to clarify the reflection process that causes positive change in student leadership behaviour. The results of a questionnaire survey conducted as part of the study were analysed. The survey was conducted in the middle of the course. The content of the study is about the change in leadership interpretation, the effect of accumulating data records in the e-portfolio used as a reflection tool, and the confidence in leadership and willingness to improve skills. First, the interpretation of leadership is considered. There are two characteristics of change. The first is from 'leadership can lead a team together and is exercised by one person who is better than others' to 'the ability that all team members need to demonstrate to achieve their goals'. The second is the shift from innate leadership skills to the interpretation that anyone can improve their skills through practice. These changes were brought about by learning through the literature on how

leadership should be at the start of the class and the content of lectures in face-to-face classes, as well as having hands-on experience of leadership in PBL activities. This change in interpretation seemed to lead to a change in the learner's self-consciousness and an attitude to look at the situation of others and the team. The weekly e-portfolio depicts an analysis of their leadership behaviour through reflection. Changes in leadership interpretation can be a factor that affects the reflection that leads to behavioural changes.

Next, the effect of accumulating learning record data in the e-portfolio is described. Learners checked the previous records at the time of reflection, compared them with the results of the time, discovered issues, and gradually learnt the learning process that leads to specific actions next time. By observing and monitoring their cognitive processes, students were able to accept and interpret the opinions of team members and adjust their behaviour. In addition, learners became more active and ambitious in PBL activities. This means that they had come to evaluate their own growth from the accumulated data, and as a result, their awareness of exerting leadership may have increased. However, subsequent behaviour depends on the attitude of self-evaluation and the viewpoint from which to judge. When trying to take on new actions, trusting in oneself to be successful can significantly contribute to motivation and achievement of goals [7]. The results of Questions 3 and 4 indicate that learners tended to have a strong desire to improve leadership.

However, some respondents did not have much sense of success when trying to exercise leadership. Keating et al. extracted three elements for the emergence of leadership behaviour: readiness – leadership self-efficacy; willingness – motivation for behaviour; and ability – leadership skills [8]. If self-efficacy influences the emergence of leadership, the breakthrough on the process of reflection that enhances self-efficacy may contribute to a positive change in leadership behaviour.

6 CONCLUSION

In this study, it was suggested that learners might change the interpretation of leadership and bring about positive behavioural changes by using e-portfolios and continuing to reflect on leadership behaviour. However, because responses to the questionnaire were voluntary, it is likely that the responding students tended to have a relatively high interest in leadership and a high willingness to acquire skills. On the other hand, the characteristics of students with such attributes are a clue to exploring the reflection process that causes positive behavioural changes in leadership behaviour. In the future, we will analyse the students' leadership behaviour frequency and reflection records concerning the prompts embedded in the e-portfolio from a quantitative and qualitative viewpoint. Furthermore, through interviews, we aim to clarify what the students were targeting in their reflection. For example, the question regarding whether students were reflecting on their internal emotion or external events was answered, in addition to how the reflection was implemented.

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